

Evaluation and Lessons Learned from the Lidar-Assisted Control Summer Games 2024

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MM92

Lidar-Assisted Control Summer Games 2024

Motivation

- ▶ already >3000 turbines running with LAC
- ▶ LAC working group: make application easy!
- ▶ together learn from Open Source tools
- ▶ develop new ideas, benchmarking
- ▶ share enthusiasm with students

- ▶ What are the main results from this challenge?
- ▶ What are the main lessons learned and how can we set up the next summer games?

Contents

1. Tools and Organization
2. Evaluation of the Summer Games
3. Main Results, Lessons Learned and Outlook

LAC OpenSource Tools

- ▶ repository and discussion forum on [GitHub](#)
- ▶ based on a repository developed by Feng Guo within the LIKE project [1] and ROSCO [2]
- ▶ Matlab/Python for simulations, Fortran for DLLs, OpenFAST with lidar simulator
- ▶ 5 examples:
 - ▶ IEA15MW_01: For “30 s sprint”
 - ▶ IEA15MW_02: EOG for FOWT
 - ▶ IEA15MW_03: For “18 m/s hurdles”
 - ▶ IEA15MW_04: Turbulent wind FOWT
 - ▶ IEA15MW_05: For “DLC 1.2 Marathon”

Categories, Disciplines, Dissemination

2 Categories (teams possible)

1. students
2. professionals

3 Disciplines

1. The 30 s Sprint
2. The 18 m/s Hurdles
3. The DLC 1.2 Marathon

Dissemination

- ▶ publish instruction on Zenodo [3] and send out via mailing lists
- ▶ include in bachelor/master course as project work, master thesis topic

The 30 s Sprint – Challenges

Task

- ▶ use of a reduced OpenFAST model (rotor and first tower fore-aft mode)
- ▶ EOG and perfect wind preview
- ▶ keep tower and rotor motion constant
- ▶ improve baseline collective pitch FF

Evaluation

- ▶ deviation from steady states
- ▶ simple cost function:

$$J = \frac{\max(|\Omega - \Omega_0|)}{\Omega_0} + \frac{\max(|M_{yT} - M_{yT0}|)}{M_{yT0}}$$

- ▶ starting point: 0.8490

Intention

Trigger new control concepts!

The 30 s Sprint – Results Students Contributions

Universidad de la República 1 🇺🇷

optimized multi-variable FF controller [4]

Universidad de la República 2 🇺🇷

NN-based pitch prediction [5]

Flensburg University of Applied Sciences 🇩🇪

NMPC based on reduced order model [6]

Ocean University of China 🇨🇳

anti-disturbance control

1. 🇺🇷 Udelar1:	0.0746	3. 🇩🇪 FUAS:	0.3110
2. 🇺🇷 Udelar2:	0.1926	4. 🇨🇳 OUC:	0.8291

The 30 s Sprint – Results Professionals Contributions

sowento 🇩🇪

optimized multi-variable FF+FB controller [7], using pitch rate and torque update proportional to wind speed changes

Shanghai Jiao Tong University 🇨🇳

optimal FF+FB using reduced model with gravity forces [8]

University of the Basque Country 🇪🇸

full NMPC with 2 DOF model and additional conventional tower damper [9]

- | | |
|-----------------------|-------------------|
| 1. 🇩🇪 sowento: 0.0798 | 3. 🇪🇸 UPV: 0.1412 |
| 2. 🇨🇳 SJTU: 0.1192 | |

The 18 m/s Hurdles – Challenges

Task

- ▶ process lidar data online or offline
- ▶ 10 min turbulent wind, 18 m/s, 6 seeds
- ▶ get the best possible wind preview (2 s)
- ▶ improve baseline lidar data processing

Evaluation

- ▶ reduce mean absolute error REWS
- ▶ simple cost function:
 $J = \text{mean} (|\text{REWS}_{\text{WF}} - \text{REWS}_{\text{LP}}|)$
- ▶ 15/12.5°, pulsed 4-beam: 0.4446
- ▶ 15°, circular CW: 0.3525

Intention

Trigger new lidar data processing techniques!

The 18 m/s Hurdles – Results

Students

- ▶ Universidad de la República: machine learning technique, 30° CW [10]
- ▶ Technical University of Denmark: grid search algorithm, pulsed 6-beam [11]
- ▶ Universidad del Norte: brute-force optimization, pulsed 4-beam [12]

Professionals

- ▶ sowento: FIR filter, 30° CW
- ▶ Molas: multi-distance, opt. pulsed, [13]
- ▶ Leice: single-distance, 15/7.5° pulsed

1. 🇇🇵 Udelar	0.1897	1. 🇩🇪 sowento	0.1893
2. 🇩🇰 DTU	0.3499	2. 🇪🇸 Molas	0.3075
3. 🇪🇸 UniNorte	0.3501	3. 🇨🇳 Leice	0.5069

The DLC 1.2 Marathon – Challenges

Task

- ▶ 11x6 simulations with turbulent wind
- ▶ full model and lidar-based wind preview
- ▶ increase energy over lifetime
- ▶ improve baseline LAC

Evaluation

- ▶ maximize energy/keep constraints:

$$J = \frac{\text{LTE} \times \text{AEP}_{\text{LAC}}}{\text{AEP}_{\text{FB}}}$$

$$\text{LTE} = \min(\text{LTE}_{\text{Tower}}, \text{LTE}_{\text{Blades}})$$

- ▶ constraints on AEP, loads, over-speed, pitch travel, generator torque
- ▶ start: 1.4335 (CW), 1.3231 (pulsed)

Intention

Benchmark full concepts!

The DLC 1.2 Marathon – Results

sowento

- ▶ 30°, circular continuous-wave lidar
- ▶ baseline lidar data processing
- ▶ baseline collective pitch feedforward
- ▶ retuned feedback controller + ≤ 6 rpm

IAV

- ▶ 15/12.5°, 4-beam pulsed lidar
- ▶ moving horizon lidar data processing
- ▶ nonlinear model predictive control
- ▶ keeping original feedback controller

1. 🇩🇪 sowento 3.3298
2. 🇩🇪 IAV 1.5340

Lessons Learned

Main questions

- ▶ What are the main results from this challenge?
- ▶ What are the main lessons learned and how can we set up the next summer games?

Main Results

- ▶ We received 15 contributions from students and professionals across 6 countries!
- ▶ LAC tools have been further extended and will be used in Summer Games 2025!
- ▶ 7 documents with further details on algorithms have been published on [Zenodo](#)!

Lessons Learned

- ▶ 30s Sprint: good results faster with optimized multi-variable FF compared to NMPC.
- ▶ 18m/s Hurdles: beam angles huge impact, baseline close to ML/frequency methods.
- ▶ DLC 1.2 Marathon: FB tuning should be done first, huge potential with FF and NMPC.
- ▶ Best integrated in project-based learning at Universities or in Master/PhD projects.
- ▶ It's challenging to have realistic meaningful tasks with reasonable time investments.

Outlook: Lidar-Assisted Control Summer Games 2025

Again three disciplines

- ▶ The 30 s sprint: now creative task.
Great for controls enthusiasts!
- ▶ The 18 m/s hurdles: now more realistic.
Great for data scientists!
- ▶ The DLC 1.2 Marathon: returned ROSCO.
Great for companies/PhD students!

How to participate?

- ▶ Try the code on [Github](#)!
- ▶ Check instruction soon on [Zenodo](#)!
- ▶ Mobilize your students and colleagues!

Acknowledgment and References

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Photo of MM92 by Marcel Schedat.

Let's work together to get
one lidar on each turbine!

Looking forward to your questions and comments!

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